

THE PROPERTIES OF STRONGLY NONEQUILIBRIUM SURFACE LAYER OF NICKEL**Korotkevich S.,**
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The evolution of structural-scale levels of deformation of the surface layer of nickel during tribotests in TsIATIM-201 lubricant has been studied. The mechanisms of formation of defect structures for various scales are indicated, the dominant role of the nanostructural scale level of deformation, leading to phase instability of the coating, is established. A quantitative assessment of the parameters of the defect structure of the surface layer of nickel was carried out.

Keywords: *dislocations, mechanisms of plastic deformation, stress fields, pores, slip bands, micro and main cracks.*

1 Introduction

Previously, the papers described the evolution of the structural-scale levels of deformation of nickel surface layer from the point of view of mesomechanics and nonequilibrium thermodynamics [1, 2]. This article describes the main mechanisms of the formation, evolution, and destruction of the structure at various structural-scale levels: nano, submicron, micro, meso, and macro. By physical mesomechanics, plastic flow in a loaded solid is a multilevel process and is associated with the loss of shear stability at nano, micro, meso, and macroscale levels [2]. Particular attention is paid to the quantitative assessment of the parameters of nanocrystalline (NC) and submicrocrystalline (SMC) structures.

To prove the receipt of a special (strong) nonequilibrium state of the surface layer of nickel with unique properties as a result of prolonged low-amplitude and alternating triboloading, we carried out a quantitative assessment of the parameters using various model concepts. Special attention is paid to the nanoscale deformation on nickel surfaces due to its unusual properties [3]. High internal stresses, dislocation density, and local curvature of the crystal lattice determine its looseness, amorphousness, catalytic activity, magnetic properties, and other anomalous physicochemical properties. In this work, the concepts of metal physics and mesomechanics are used to prove the existence of a strong nonequilibrium surface layer of nickel under conditions of its phase instability at stresses comparable to and exceeding the modulus of elasticity of nickel (ca. $2 \cdot 10^{11}$ Pa).

This work aims to quantitatively estimate the parameters of the elements of the defect structure of the nickel surface layer.

2 Experimental

The effectiveness of research on the physical laws of plastic deformation, hardening, and destruction of surface layers of solids under their frictional loading is largely determined by the level of experimental research due to the correctness of the methods used the correctness and sufficient sensitivity of the applied research methods. To solve the problem of hardening and

destruction of surface layers of metals under frictional loading, we used a wide range of modern physical research methods, such as ferromagnetic resonance (FMR), transmission electron microscopy, X-ray structural and metallographic analyses, electron diffraction of medium and low energies, etc. [3]. To the specifics of the problems to be solved and the properties of the objects under study, in some cases, it was required to create specialized equipment [4]. Therefore, a technique for estimating the density of dislocations was developed, and a ferromagnetic resonance facility was created [4]. For electron microscopic studies of the structure, the "transmission" methods were improved, and tribometric installations for testing samples and one-sided electrolytic thinning were created [4].

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) methods have been widely used in the study of the kinetics of wear of surface layers under friction loading [4]. The complex of these methods, along with transmission electron microscopy, made it possible to establish the relationship between the microstructure of the surface layers of solids with changes in the lubricating medium and the kinetics of wear.

Nickel samples were disks with a diameter of about 0.006 m and a thickness of about 0.001 m. Disks with a diameter of 5–6 mm² were cut out from nickel foil with a purity of 99.99 %, obtained by electron-beam melting by the electrospark method. Before friction testing, the samples were electrolytically polished and annealed in a vacuum of 0.133 MPa at 973 K. The friction test was carried out on an AE-5 machine with a precision setting of the contact plane. Triboloading of Ni-Mo pair sliding was carried out mainly in TsIATIM-201 grease at a nominal pressure of 84 and 168 kPa and a linear velocity of ≈ 0.5 m/s. The experimental technique is similar to that described in the paper [3].

Experimental FMR methods are the most convenient for studying the dislocation structure of ferromagnets since at the frequency of the external electromagnetic field $\nu = 9600$ MHz, the broadening of the resonance absorption line in a deformed ferromagnet is

caused by the elastic fields of dislocations [3]. In these works, a relationship was established between the FMR line width (ΔH) and the dislocation density (ρ). In the deformation range $\varepsilon \approx 0-75\%$, there is a linear relationship between line broadening and dislocation density. The absence of line broadening in a deformed ferromagnet with a magnetostriction constant equal to zero (permalloy) confirms the physical meaning of broadening ΔH due to local magnetic fields around dislocations [3].

The penetration depth (δ) of a microwave (micro-wave) field in metallic materials is $\delta = 10^{-7}-10^{-6}$ m. This determines the selectivity of the method in terms of the information content of the defective microstructure of thin surface layers, especially under frictional loading, when plastic deformation covers layers commensurate with the thickness of the skin layer [4]. In accordance with the above provisions of FMR and direct electron microscopic studies, the observed cyclic dependence $\Delta H = f(t)$ reflects the kinetics of the dislocation structure in the surface layer of frictionally loaded nickel.

Electron microscopic studies of nickel were carried out on an EVM-100AK microscope using the "transmission" method of thin foils and Hitachi H-800. Foils were obtained by one-sided electrolytic thinning of discs on the opposite side from the friction surface on a jet polishing unit equipped with a sensitive photodiode bridge, which makes it possible to control the transparency of areas at a depth of ca. 0.1 μm from the friction loading surface. The dislocation density was

determined, including by micrographs, using mutually perpendicular secants. Data on the density of dislocations were obtained by averaging, during analysis, at least five local areas in different grains.

3 Results and Discussions

The work of the friction force was estimated by the equation:

$$E_{fr} = A = F_{fr} \cdot l, \quad (1)$$

where F_{fr} is the friction force, and l is the friction path.

The evaluation of the work of the friction force is 18 kJ with a friction coefficient $\mu = 0.12$ and a friction time of 108 ks. The friction path was 76032 m. It is necessary to take into account that 90 % of the energy accumulated (E_{ac}) in the surface layer of the metal is spent with the layer-by-layer mechanism for its destruction [5]. The value of the accumulated energy during friction loading, accumulated by the sublayers, corresponds to $\approx 10\%$ of the calculated value (E_{calc}) of the energy, which is numerically equal to the work of the friction force by expression (1) [6]. The distribution of the accumulated energy value over the thickness of the surface layer is shown in Table 1.

Analysis of the ratio of the calculated energy accumulated in the surface layer ($E_{ac} = 1.7 \text{ kJ/cm}^3$) to the binding energy of nickel atoms $U = 422 \text{ kJ/mol}$ allows us to conclude the strong nonequilibrium structural state and properties of this layer.

Table 1.

The ratio of the energy accumulated (E_{ac}) in the surface layer to the binding energy of nickel atoms (U_b) depending on the layer thickness (h).

h , 10^{-6} m	S , 10^{-6} m ²	V , 10^{-12} m ³	v , 10^{-6} mol	m , 10^{-9} kg	$E_{fr} \cdot 10^7$, J/mol	$E_{ac} \cdot 10^7$, J/mol	E_{ac}/U_b
0.01	28.3	0.283	0.043	1.84	42500	4250	$\approx 10^5$
0.1	28.3	2.83	0.43	18.4	3950	395	$\approx 10^4$
1.0	28.3	28.3	4.3	184	400	40	$\approx 10^3$
10	28.3	282.7	42.8	1837	40	4.0	$\approx 10^2$
100	28.3	2827.35	428.4	18372	4.0	0.4	≈ 10
1000	28.3	28273.5	4284	183721	0.4	0.04	≈ 1.0

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Using three independent model concepts, we will estimate the value of internal stresses in the surface layer of nickel.

A quantitative assessment of local internal stresses was carried out using the relations of string theory [7], where the equilibrium of a segment of a dislocation loop (Fig. 1) is established under the action of external and intrinsic stress or linear tension.

Figure 1. Dislocation loops of the Frank–Read type and nanobands (white arrows)

Under the influence of static stress σ_B , the dislocation string bends to the radius of curvature r_o , which is determined from the relation:

$$\frac{E_l}{r_o} = b\sigma_B, \quad (2)$$

where b is the Burgers vector, and E_l is the linear tension determined from the relation:

$$E_l = \frac{G}{2}b^2, \quad (3)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the crystal lattice of nickel.

At $b = 50 \text{ nm}$, $G = 77 \text{ GPa}$, and $r_o = 1200 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 1), the stress value, σ_B , is $2 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Pa}$, equal to the value of the elastic modulus of nickel.

The second method for assessing internal stresses is associated with assessing the local curvature of the

crystal lattice in zones of severe plastic deformation. It should be noted that in all metallic materials obtained as a result of plastic deformation by different methods, the indispensable characteristics of SMC structures are subgrain boundaries with variable misorientation vectors (ϑ) or accumulations of continuously distributed partial disclinations [8–10]. The characteristic of the effective density of continuously distributed partial disclinations is the components of the curvature tensor in the vicinity of the boundary $\partial\vartheta/\partial r \approx \chi_{ij}$.

In the general case, special methods were used to analyze high continuous misorientations (Fig. 2) with high orientation gradients (Fig. 2, a). In the case of a combination of continuous and discrete misorientations shown in Figure 2, b, the components of the curvature tensor are determined by the expression [8–10]:

$$\chi_{ij} = \Delta\omega_i/\Delta x_j, \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ means averaging the misorientation angle for some characteristic region Δx .

Figure 2. Diagrams of structural states with high local gradients of crystal lattice orientation: substructure with high continuous misorientations (A) and substructure with continuous and discrete misorientations (B).

As a rule, in this case, the values of the curvature gradient ($-\nabla \cdot \chi$) turn out to be non-zero. Then, the misorientation of subgrains can be described in terms of the continuum density of disclinations (ϑ), and the expression [11] must be satisfied [11]:

$$\vartheta = -\nabla \cdot \chi^{PL}. \quad (5)$$

In the areas of the surface layer adjacent to the microbands, there is a dissipative subgrain microstructure (SMC structure) with a block size $d = 0.05 - 0.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Subgrain microstructure ($t = 50.7 \cdot 10^3$ s)

This microstructure is characterized by a quasi-regular arrangement of dislocation tangles. An estimate of the components of the curvature tensor χ lying in the plane of figure (3) using relation (7) shows that χ_{12} reaches values of about 1 degree/nm, and χ_{21} reaches values of about 1.3 degree/nm, and the curvature gradient estimated from expression (5) is $\vartheta \approx 0.01$ degree/nm². This state can be characterized as a structural state with a very high continuum density of disclinations. These structural states are characterized by high local stresses. Using the continuum theory of defects, these stresses can be estimated by the following equation [8–10]:

$$\sigma_{lok} \approx \chi_{ij} E \Delta h / 2, \quad (6)$$

where E is the Young modulus, and Δh is the characteristic dimensions of the zone of high curvature of the lattice, the value of σ_{loc} in zones with elements of plastic distortion, highlighted by white ovals in Fig. 3, reaches very high values of $10^{12} - 10^{13}$ Pa.

The stress gradient is calculated by the following equation:

$$\partial \sigma_{loc} / \partial r \approx (E / 2\pi) (\partial \vartheta / \partial r). \quad (7)$$

The stress gradient is estimated at $\approx 3.2 \cdot 10^{19}$ Pa/m. Let us estimate the stress gradient in a different way, based on the definition of the gradient as the ratio of the stress difference to the distance. The pressure value in the middle of the white circle (Fig. 3) is $10^{12} - 10^{13}$ Pa, based on the calculation by Eq. (6). The theoretical strength of nickel at which a crack is formed (Fig. 3) is $9.8 \cdot 10^9$ N/m². The stress ratio is approxi-

mately three orders of magnitude. The distance between the crack tip and the selected area of the white circle is $\approx 0.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m (see Fig. 3). The voltage gradient value is ca. $10^{18} - 10^{19}$ Pa/m. It can be assumed that the waves of plastic distortion, presented in the area of the white circle, appear under the condition that the stress gradient is comparable in order of magnitude to or exceeds the theoretical strength of the metal (see Fig. 3).

There is a third technique for quantifying stresses using extinction contours. To determine the magnitude of internal stresses, a method of restoring stresses from the curvature of the crystal lattice arising from the deformation of a polycrystalline material is used, i.e., by the parameters of bending extinction contours observed in the electron microscopic image. Extinction contours reflect the nature of deformation of local regions of the sample, which can be both plastic and elastic-plastic. The known types of deformation of the crystal lattice are bending and torsion. To determine the contributions to the plastic component of internal stresses, the technique proposed in the paper was used [12]. The values of internal stresses during bending and torsion are calculated by the following equations [12]:

$$\sigma_{11} = E \sqrt{b \chi_{11}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{12} = E \sqrt{b \chi_{12}}, \quad (9)$$

where E is the modulus of elasticity, b is the Burgers vector, and χ_{11} , χ_{12} are the components of the curvature-torsion tensor of the crystal lattice.

The width of the contour can be represented through the components ΔL_{pl} on the axis of the Cartesian coordinate system. Then, the plastic components of the curvature-torsion gradient at bending χ_{11} and torsion χ_{12} of the crystal lattice, respectively, are determined by the following equations:

$$\chi_{11} = \frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta L_x}, \quad (10)$$

$$\chi_{12} = \frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta L_y}, \quad (11)$$

A – extinction contours at friction time $t = 108 \cdot 10^3$ s

B – regions of local curvature and extinction contours

Figure 4. Images of the nickel surface obtained by transmission electron microscopy

The high local curvature of the area marked in Fig. 4, B by an oval indicates high values of internal stresses. Estimation of the values of internal stresses along extinction contours (Fig. 4, B, the area of the oval and arrows) shows that they are in the range ($4 \cdot 10^{11}$ Pa– $1.7 \cdot 10^{12}$ Pa), which is two to three orders of magnitude higher than the value of the ultimate strength of nickel ca. 0.5 GPa.

Estimating the values of internal stresses of extinction contours (Fig. 4, A and B) shows that they are in the range (10^{11} – 10^{12}) Pa. Based on the results of a quantitative assessment of the structure parameters, it is of interest to determine the contributions of the hardening mechanisms according to the equation, which practically includes all contributions that determine the resistance to deformation of nickel at the yield point [13]: μm

$$\sigma_{\Sigma} = \sigma_{fr} + \sigma_{hard} + \sigma_{grain} + \sigma_{Or} + \sqrt{(\sigma_{field}^2 + \sigma_{forest}^2)}, \quad (14)$$

Here, σ_{fr} is the friction stress of dislocations in the Ni crystal lattice; σ_{hard} is a hardening of a Ni sample with atoms of alloying elements (C, Mn, V, and others), σ_{forest} is a strengthening by forest dislocations, which

where $\Delta\varphi$ is the misorientation angle across the width of the contour ΔL ; ΔL is the value of the width of the bending extinction contour.

Let us give an example of calculating the values of internal stresses for an extinction circuit (Fig. 4, A, lower arrow) following the procedure described in [12]:

$$\chi = 83^\circ / 100 \text{ nm} \approx 0.8 \text{ degree/nm}, \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma = 2 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Pa} (100 \text{ nm} \cdot 0.8 \text{ degree/nm})^{1/2} \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ Pa}, \quad (13)$$

cut the sliding dislocations, σ_{field} is a hardening by internal long-range stress fields, σ_{Or} is a hardening by incoherent particles bypassing them by dislocations according to the Orowan mechanism (disperse hardening), and σ_{grain} is a hardening due to grain boundaries.

Let us estimate the contribution of each of the hardening factors. First, it is grain boundary hardening assessed using the Hall–Petch relationship [13]:

$$\sigma_{grain} = \sigma_0 + kd^{-1/2}, \quad (15)$$

where σ_0 is the resistance to deformation; $k = 0.18 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$ coefficient; d is the average grain size. Strengthening due to grain boundaries $\sigma_{grain} = 1 \div 2 \text{ GPa}$.

Second, an important contribution to the hardening of the nickel surface is made by forest dislocations, both of an unpolarized (or uncharged) and polarized (or charged) dislocation ensemble. It creates a shear stress determined by the following equation [13]:

$$\sigma_{forest} = m \cdot \alpha \cdot G \cdot b \cdot \sqrt{\rho}, \quad (16)$$

where m is the orientation factor, or the Schmid factor, $m = 2.2$; α is a dimensionless coefficient that varies within 0.05 – 0.6 depending on the type of dislocation ensemble [13] (we will take it equal to 0.25 [13]), $G = 78$ GPa is the shear modulus of the matrix material, $b = 0.35$ nm is the lattice constant of nickel, and ρ is the average value of the scalar dislocation density. The scalar dislocation density is very high and is in the region of $\rho \approx 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$. The quantitative estimate is in the range $\sigma_{forest} = 15\text{--}50$ GPa.

The value of σ_l corresponds to a charged dislocation ensemble of dislocations and is estimated by electron microscopy from bending extinction contours [13]:

$$\sigma_{forest} = m \cdot \alpha_c \cdot G \cdot b \cdot \sqrt{\rho_{\pm}}, \quad (17)$$

where $\alpha_c = 0.5$ is the Strunin coefficient.

An external contact effect on the nickel surface at a very long friction time $t = 108 \cdot 10^3$ s and more in the presence of surfactants contained in the CIATIM-201 plastic lubricant leads to the formation of a highly developed submicrostructure, which causes the interaction of long-range dislocation fields, the polarization of the dislocation structure, which is reflected in the appearance of extinction contours upon irradiation with an electron flow of a nickel sample. A quantitative estimate of the curvature-torsion parameter from the analysis of images of extinction contours shows that it is up to 1–3 degree/nm at a voltage of up to 10^{12} Pa. The excess dislocation density is 10^{18} m^{-2} . A quantitative estimate of the magnitude of stresses σ_{field} , carried out for $\chi = 3$ degree/nm, is ≈ 76 GPa. The quantitative estimate is in the range of 36–76 GPa.

The estimate of the term $\sqrt{(\sigma_{forest}^2 + \sigma_{field}^2)}$ shows that it is in the range from 50 to 98 GPa. The contribution from the term σ_{tr} , which takes into account the presence and concentration of other elements C, Mn, V, and others, is very small and can be neglected since the concentration of Ni atoms is 99.99 %. The contribution from the term σ_{fr} , which takes into account the friction stress of nickel dislocations, is about 30 MPa and can be neglected. The contribution from the term σ_{O_2} can be neglected since there are no carbide phases of Ni compounds with carbon in nickel.

Thus, the quantitative assessment of the contributions in expression (14) will be determined by three terms, namely: $\sqrt{(\sigma_{field}^2 + \sigma_{forest}^2)}$, σ_{grain} , and σ_{fr} . Thus, the quantitative assessment of the contributions in expression (14) will be determined by three terms, namely: $\sqrt{(\sigma_{field}^2 + \sigma_{forest}^2)}$, σ_{grain} , and σ_{fr} . The main contribution is made by two terms $\sqrt{(\sigma_{field}^2 + \sigma_{forest}^2)}$ and σ_{grain} . The total σ_{Σ} is in the range from 51 to 99 GPa.

It should be noted that this result is of an approximate nature. The main contribution to the hardening

mechanism is made by the component from the dislocation of the forest and the dislocation ensemble.

The directly proportional relationship between the broadening of the FMR line (ΔH) and the degree of deformation (ε) is fulfilled under the triboloading of a nickel sample. The dislocation density is directly proportional to the deformation, and the relation is fulfilled [14]:

$$\rho = \rho_o + A\varepsilon, \quad (18)$$

where ρ is the dislocation density, A is a constant, and ε is the relative deformation.

Constant A is determined from the ratio:

$$A = \beta/d, \quad (19)$$

where β is a constant, and d is the grain diameter. Using the Hall–Petch equation, we obtain [14]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_o + \alpha\mu b\rho^{1/2}, \quad (20)$$

where $\alpha = 0.5$, μ is the shear modulus, and b is the Burgers vector. Since the value of σ_o is much less than the second term in expression (20), then the expression is fulfilled [14]:

$$\sigma \approx \alpha\mu b\rho^{1/2}, \quad (21)$$

At stresses varying in the $10^{11}\text{--}10^{12}$ Pa range, the dislocation density reaches 10^{18}m^{-2} , which is two to three orders of magnitude higher than the dislocation density obtained during severe plastic deformation by equal channel pressing or in a Bridgman mill [15]. Suppose we assume that the value of the dislocation density reaches a certain critical value at the selective mechanism of wear [16]. In that case, achieving such high values of internal stress is possible due to an increase in the value of the Burgers vector and, accordingly, the amorphousness of the surface layer of the metal.

Large shifts in the crystal lattice of the surface layer of nickel, carried out by shifting and rotating submicrostructural elements, cause the presence of stacking faults and twins. Since the crystal structure of a solid is determined by its electronic subsystem, the creation of a fragment of another structure in a deformation defect is also reflected in the electronic energy spectrum of the crystal. Any deformation defect causes local curvature of the crystal lattice, which is especially clearly seen in areas of very high stresses, which relax through the formation of pores (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Inter- and transcrystalline destruction

The displacement of atoms in vapors during the development of shear deformation will be accompanied by plastic distortion in the zone of interstitial bifurcation minima of the many-particle potential. The latter

causes the vorticity of the plastic flow and, as a consequence, is accompanied by a high local curvature of the surface layer and corrugation of the surface (Fig. 6) [17].

A bifurcation interstitial structural states

Figure 6. Generation of bifurcation interstitial structural states (A), where «A» – «H» are clusters of positive ions at the grain boundary 1 and 2 (A), in the zones of local curvature of the crystal lattice during the formation of a nickel surface with nanostructured formations, which is represented by a three-dimensional AFM image (B)

Large shifts of the crystal lattice of the nickel surface layer, carried out by shifting and rotating submicrostructural elements (Fig. 4, A, arrow above), cause the presence of packing defects and twins. Since the crystal structure of a solid is determined by its electronic subsystem, creating a fragment of another structure in a deformation defect is also reflected in the electron-energy spectrum of the crystal [17]. A deformation

defect, for example, a packing defect, causes a local curvature of the crystal lattice. High stresses in the surface layer relax through the formation of pores. The presence of the packing defects (Fig. 8, A, big arrow) directly confirms the loss of shear stability of the crystal lattice of nickel [3].

Figure 7. Microstructure of slip bands. Packing defect (arrow).

The calculation of the stacking fault energy (γ) was carried out based on the equality of the forces of mutual elastic repulsion of the partial Shockley dislocations, between which the stacking fault lies and the surface tension forces contracting the stacking fault. The expression used [18]:

$$\gamma = \frac{\alpha G b^2}{R}, \quad (22)$$

where α is a coefficient lying in the range from 0.5 to 1, G is the shear modulus of the crystal lattice in this case of nickel, b is the Burgers vector, and R is the distance between partial dislocations. A quantitative estimate shows that $\gamma \approx 50 \div 100 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. The quantity of stacking fault energy of the crystal lattice of nickel has decreased at least three times, confirming the crystal

lattice's special nonequilibrium state. Diffusion of surface-active substance in a high nonequilibrium structure leads to a significant decrease in stacking fault energy and, consequently, can lead to a decrease in the material's elastic modulus.

The formed nonequilibrium nano and submicrostructured surface passes to the non-dislocation deformation mechanism by propagating nonlinear waves of structural transformations. In the zones of localization of distortions, the stored energy dissipates through the formation of nanodipoles (Fig. 8, A–C). These defects represent pairs of dangling boundaries of misorientation of opposite signs. The advancement of nonlinear waves of plastic distortion carries out a shift with the reorientation of the crystal lattice and leaves the nanobands with a length of a localized zone of $\approx 20\text{--}100 \text{ nm}$. The width of one nanoband is several nanometers. The length of the nanoband is tens of nanometers ($\approx 20\text{--}40 \text{ nm}$, Fig. 8, C).

Figure 8. Propagation of nonlinear waves of plastic distortion in the regions of the local curvature of the crystal lattice at friction loading $t = 133 \text{ ks}$ (A–C)

An increase in temperature activates physicochemical processes on the surface, which contributes to the transition of atoms from the nodes of the crystal lattice to interstitial bifurcation structural states. Tubular diffusion causes plastic distortion and the movement of nonequilibrium point defects, which determine the nonlinear dynamics of structure formation of NC and SMC structures, as well as the formation of porosity. The kinetics of structure formation and the mechanism of its destruction proceed in accordance with the energy ad-

vantage and the Hamilton principle [19]. The latter implies the existence of invariants, which are described in the paper [20].

4 Conclusions

The displacement of ions from the sites of the crystal lattice the formation of nanocluster states consisting of clusters of ions screened by an electron gas, is indisputable evidence loss of strength of the crystal lattice of a metal (nickel). At the sites of displacement, nano- and submicropores are formed. Combining the latter leads to the dispersion of the crystal lattice. Its

strength is lost, and increased porosity and looseness appear. The presence of twins along slip bands and stacking faults confirms the strong nonequilibrium state of the crystal lattice of the surface layer of nickel. Amorphous properties appear, confirmed by non-crystallographic shifts of local structural transformations.

A quantitative assessment of the parameters of the nickel surface layer defect structure under the conditions of its phase instability in fields of high local stresses has been carried out. The formation of nanostructural states is characterized by:

- the high density of structural defects: split dislocations ($\rho \approx 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$), disclinations with discrete disorientation boundaries, pores, atom-vacancy structural states, twins, stacking faults, point defects, etc.;
- the local gradient of orientation of boundaries of structural elements $\chi = 1\text{--}3$ degree/nm;
- high values of stresses comparable to and exceeding the modulus of elasticity of the crystal lattice of nickel (ca. $2 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Pa}$);
- through (tubular) diffusion and mass transfer in fields of high gradients of local stresses;
- a decrease in the level of activation energy for relaxation processes, for example, a decrease in at least 3 times the value of the stacking fault energy in the crystal lattice of nickel;
- dynamic micro-recrystallization;
- high-velocity sensitivity (the velocity of dislocation movement increased by at least 8 times) under conditions of amorphization and the quasi-viscous mechanism of their destruction;
- reduction of the period of change in the strength properties of the nickel surface by 8 times.

Thus, on the basis of a quantitative analysis of the parameters of a strong nonequilibrium nickel surface layer defect structure, it has been convincingly shown that it is impossible to exist and describe it without using the classical concepts of dislocation theory and mesomechanics, namely: the term dispersed crystal lattice of metal (nickel) at all structural-scale levels of deformation. The system tends to pass into a new structural state by the scaling of the local curvature of the crystal lattice at all structural-scale levels of plastic deformation and destruction of the metal surface. The nanoscale level leads to the hierarchical self-organization of multilevel processes, where interstitial bifurcation structural states arise in the zones of local curvature of the crystal lattice. The development of plastic distortion and the mechanisms of motion of nonequilibrium point defects determine the nonlinear dynamics of structure formation and the process of wear of surface layers in accordance with mesomechanics and nonequilibrium thermodynamics.

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curvature of the crystal lattice and the mechanism for the formation of these states are described in the paper [17]. The authors have no conflicts of interest related to this article. Acknowledgement

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Statements and Declarations

The authors declare they have no financial interests.

Competing Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Author contributions

Conceptualization and Methodology: Sergy Korotkevich, Yauheni Kavaliou; Formal analysis and investigation: Writing - original draft preparation: Yauheni Kavaliou, Aliaksandr Kupo; Writing - review and editing: Yauheni Kavaliou, Aliaksandr Kupo; Funding acquisition and Resources: Sergy Korotkevich, Aliaksandr Kupo; Supervision: Sergy Korotkevich.

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